

Identifying research contributions based on semantic analysis of citation sentences: A case study of the 2021 Physiology or Medicine Nobel Prize laureates

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Abstract

Prior research in identifying research contributions has extracted contributions based on the academic paper itself. In this study, we aim to explore the research contributions from the perspective of the external citation environment (citation sentences in this article), with the attainment of two 2021 Physiology or Medicine Nobel Prize laureates and their academic papers used as an experimental case. First, we analyze the features of texts indicating research contributions in academic papers, and then construct a model to identify citation sentences describing the significance of contributions in all the citing literature. In addition, we make a sentence-level contribution analysis of the important information contained in the contribution sentences. Finally, the clustering method is utilized to group similar contribution sentences into research contribution points, which allow us to automatically summarize the research contributions of the two laureates and compare these concluded contribution points to the award ceremony speech for validation. The set of approaches suggested in this work for identifying research contributions in academic papers could contribute significant semantic assessment data to reforming and rebuilding the research evaluation system.

Keywords: Research Contribution, Nobel Articles, Citation Sentence, Semantic Analysis

Introduction

Research contributions, which indicate how a research paper contributes new knowledge or new understanding compared to previous research on the topic, are the most useful sort of information for researchers to comprehend the paper's primary substance (H. Chen, Nguyen, & Alghamdi, 2022). An important research challenge in the realm of library and information science is how to mine research contributions from academic papers. Identifying research contributions at the level of the content from academic articles will provide essential semantic assessment material to promote the reform and reconstruction of the research evaluation system. The value of contribution in an academic paper is reflected in the social and economic benefits of the author's innovative contributions, such as new theories, new techniques, new technologies, new discoveries, and new applications, to the advancement of human civilization and science and technology (Luo, Cai, Qian, & Lu, 2021). These contributions are often expressed in an academic paper's abstract, introduction, or conclusion, and may also be distributed across the paper's sections. Consequently, researchers usually conduct research contribution element identification studies on a certain scale of abstract or full-text datasets, by summarizing some signature words and general patterns representing research contribution statements. On this basis, they annotate a small-scale contribution sentence set and construct identification models. However, the method described above for identifying research contributions is based solely on the academic paper itself, and the research contributions described by the paper authors themselves are the primary focus, so the identified research contributions may be subject to some degree of subjectivity.

With the gradual opening up of full-text data, it is possible to mine the research contributions from academic papers based on citation content. A citation sentence is a descriptive or evaluative text for the cited paper with a citation mark. It documents the flow of knowledge, and the cited information is often viewed as significant by peer academics; hence, a valuable citation sentence can truly reflect the significance of the work to the advancement of science. In contrast, it is more scientifically sound to identify the scientific contribution of an academic paper based on its external evaluation (main focus on citation sentences in this study) than to investigate the scientific contribution of the paper itself.

The Nobel Prize is one of the most prestigious awards a scientist may get for his or her research contributions. This study, therefore, employs Nobel Prize papers as experimental subjects and identifies the research contribution sentences of publications citing a Nobel article prior to its author's investiture, for instance, “... *the 1997 cloning of the capsaicin receptor, now termed TRPV1, represented a major breakthrough in understanding the transduction of noxious stimuli in the periphery. [20]*”. Due to the outstanding contribution in the related field of the Nobel Prize, laureates' publications are frequently mentioned, hence providing a rich supply of citation sentences for our research.

This study proposes a method to identify research contributions in academic papers based on the semantic analysis of citation sentences, so as to obtain an objective evaluation of the cited papers from the perspective of the scientific community. To be specific, we first construct a model to identify research contribution sentences (hereinafter referred to as “contribution sentence”) from the external citation context of academic papers, and then summarize these contribution sentences into several contribution points based on a topic modeling technique, which includes two steps of clustering and class label extraction. This study concludes with an empirical investigation to determine the research contributions of the two 2021 Physiology or Medicine Nobel Prize laureates. We confirm the verification of our method by comparing the identified research contributions to the Nobel press release. The method overcomes the limitation of identifying research contributions just from the academic paper itself, and it may also give evidence to support the future comprehensive evaluation of papers and talents.

Related work

Analysis and identification of research contributions is a novel field that has lately gained traction. We have grouped it into two implementation paths, one of which is based on peer review, where scholars in the relevant area conduct an in-depth examination and summary of a particular paper's research contribution. For instance, Auer et al. (2018) developed the open research knowledge graph (ORKG), in which the features and values of each paper's essential contribution were summarized by the paper's author. Even across articles, contributions to the ORKG were related via the graph. While writing an academic literature review, it helps scholars in comparing the research contributions of several works (Oelen, Jaradeh, Farfar, Stocker, & Auer, 2019).

The other strategy is to mechanically extract components or phrases of innovative contribution by using a variety of technological methods, these studies focus mostly on signature features that emerge in the literature. L. Chen & Fang (2019) evaluated the innovative contribution of topic words by extracting N-grams as candidate contribution points from the discourse structure and verifying their presence in the Scopus database. H. Chen et al. (2022) defined six categories of research contributions for academic literature in the computing domain and provided a fine-grained research contribution sentence annotation scheme based on the ACL corpus. Also, annotations were performed by them on a high-quality research contribution dataset of 5024

sentences. Le et al. (2019) employed a rule-based method to extract research contribution points from citation sentences in academic papers to evaluate the academic worth of cited articles. Roger, Luigi, & Claudio (2021) proposed CiTelling: a radically new model of fine-grained semantic structures lying behind citational sentences able to represent their intent and features, and these features include methods, models, and other points of research contribution. Hua & Shin (2021) developed a list of prompt words for sentences describing originality (SDO) in the academic paper and utilized these guidelines to locate and extract sentences describing uniqueness from the paper. Combining features such as word frequency, TF-IDF, and sentence length, Wang, See-To, Lin, & Li (2018) formulated criteria for extracting research highlight sentences. Fisas, Saggion, & Ronzano (2015) employed the method of logistic regression and support vector machines to classify sentences after manually annotating research background sentences, research method sentences, and contribution sentences of articles in the field of computer graphics.

In general, the majority of investigations have been done on full-text articles in order to annotate datasets and train models around some signature features of research contribution elements. By contrast, the method presented in this study is based on a semantic analysis of citation sentences. The method will automatically identify sentences and phrases that explain research contributions in academic papers. This way provides a good complement and validation to the research contributions identified based on their own content while ensuring the relative objectivity and authenticity of the identification results.

The method of research contribution identification

The research contribution corresponds to the discoveries, methods, and ideas presented in the article, and the task of this paper is to identify these elements from the standpoint of external citation. To be specific, we first need to annotate contribution sentences manually and then construct a model to identify the text of research contribution descriptions by analyzing the semantic features in the cited sentences of research papers. During the process of annotating, we summarized the differences between contribution sentences and general citation sentences, extracted the signature features such as signature words, phrases, and sentence patterns, and further integrated these signature features into the research contribution sentence identification model to enhance its identifying performance. Although contribution sentences are rich in valuable information, it is difficult to summarize these contributions entirely by hand because of the large number of sentences. Thus, we use the clustering method for summarizing contribution sentences into several classes and give each class a label as the contribution point automatically. We make an empirical study of the research contributions of two 2021 Physiology or Medicine Nobel Prize laureates. For the research contributions of the two laureates from the external environment, it should be obtained from the evaluation description that is constantly cited in subsequent articles for their key publications. In this case, we will utilize the research contribution identification model mentioned above to extract contribution sentences from those citing papers, then we try to understand the specific contribution that two laureates have made to the field in question by analyzing these sentences. On this basis, we filter laureates' representative works according to the ranking of the number of their contribution sentences. On the other hand, the research contribution points from the sentences that cite these representative works, are further clustered and summarized in several aspects. At last, this paper verifies the efficacy of the proposed method in identifying research contributions by comparing it with the Nobel press release. The overall research idea is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The idea of research contribution identification for the two 2021 Physiology or Medicine Nobel Prize laureates

The construction of the research contribution identification model

Based on the above-mentioned designed idea of research contribution recognition, the research contribution recognition model to be built in this study can be divided into three parts. The first is to build a training data set for research contribution in order to provide a high-quality corpus for subsequent model training; The second is to build a contribution sentence recognition model to identify the contribution sentences of cited papers; The third is to use a topic modeling technique to sum up the contribution sentences into few research contribution points and generate a label to each point. Following are further details of these three components.

Construction of training dataset for contribution sentences

A task-adapted corpus of high quality is fundamental to building deep learning models. Due to the lack of publicly available corpora, this paper needs to first collect some highly cited papers (e.g., Nobel Prize, etc.) that have made important contributions in related fields as the gold standard dataset. After that, the cited papers in the gold standard dataset are screened for citation sentences expressing research contributions, and then manually discriminated and annotated in order to train a contribution sentence identification model. In turn, the model is then used to iteratively annotate the training data, and the process is repeated until the model achieves good recognition performance.

Based on the PubMed Central (PMC) open full-text database, we downloaded the XML files of its full-text data and parsed them, extracting the citation sentences and the information for each cited article, to which these sentences refer, to build a citation sentence database. According to statistics, we have parsed 2,162,734 full-text articles in total, which were published between 1781 and 2021. with a focus on 2006-2021 (articles for 2021 were incomplete), and the average annual number of articles published was up to several hundred thousand. We saved the meta data of these articles, including pmc, pmid, title, abstract, author, journal information and other ten fields totally. In addition, we wrote rules to extract all citation sentences in one paper and located their citation information according to the citation tag that appeared in the citation sentence. Also, we stored the citation sentences and citation information in the database. The citation sentence database includes three fields: id, senId, and cite_sen,

with a total of 110,410,852 records shown in Figure 2; the citation information database includes cid, pmcid, senId, refid, pmid_cited, title author, year_pub, journal, and journal_type, with a total of 82,493,341 records.

On the other hand, it is necessary to find highly cited papers, which have made great contributions to related fields, as the gold standard collection. So that we can manually annotate contribution sentences from papers that cite the collection. The Nobel Prize is often considered to be one of the most prestigious, longest-time series, and largest volume of prizes in the world, and is often awarded only to scholars who have made the most significant contributions to their field. As one of the most recognized scientific prizes, the Nobel Prize laureates, and their major works have been the focus of research due to their high influence and outstanding research contributions. Since most of the papers in the PubMed database are related to the medical field, only the main works of the Nobel Laureates in medicine are selected for this study. We collected 77 key publications of Physiology or Medicine Nobel Prize laureates from 1990 to 2021, which are provided by the official website of the Nobel Prize, and found the corresponding pmid of each publication in PMC. Then we selected citation sentences of each publication from our citation sentences database according to the pmid, and a total of 10,767 citation sentences were queried in the database, we used a random sampling method to annotate the citation sentences one by one.

id	senId	cite_sen
10983	A_B_9d8679ca-d8ea-	Price indexes for traded food commodities are widely reported by international agencies
10984	A_B_9d86d29e-d8ea-	Formulas to aggregate individual items into price indexes were first introduced more than
10985	A_B_9d8bec48-d8ea-	The purpose of most price indexes is to capture changes in the cost of what is actually
10986	A_B_9d8c2c30-d8ea-	The aim of this paper is to develop improved indexes for the cost of a nutritious diet rel
10987	A_B_9d966916-d8ea-	Soon after the discovery of essential nutrients, Stigler (1945) pioneered the developme
10988	A_B_9d96b0a6-d8ea-	Allen (2017) uses this kind of price index for poverty measurement, and others use thes
10989	A_B_9d96c3ca-d8ea-	At the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA), the "Minimum-Cost Food Plan"
10990	A_B_9d96d450-d8ea-	The same method is used internationally, for example to make recommendations in Der
10991	A_B_9d96e242-d8ea-	One of the most important uses for least-cost diets is to help nutrition assistance progr
10992	A_B_9da0e1c0-d8ea-	The specific criteria we use in this paper are from the Minimum Diet Diversity for Wome
10993	A_B_9da12ee6-d8ea-	This has been linked to nutrient adequacy in several low-income countries (Arimond et
10994	A_B_9da146b0-d8ea-	For example, the standard international indicator for dietary diversity in children aged 6
10995	A_B_9da6b834-d8ea-	Overall inflation is based on average expenditure in each country as computed by the In
10996	A_B_9dbc89de-d8ea-	Actual diets may exceed or fall short of any given nutritional standard, and methods de
10997	A_B_9dbce000-d8ea-	Apart from those two price indices presented here, parallel work is under way to constr
10998	A_B_9dce9f0c-d8ea-	This method is unlikely to truncate seasonal extremes, as mangoes in Ghana generally
10999	A_B_9dd8980e-d8ea-	To compute the price indexes, the price of each food was converted from reported unit
11000	A_B_9dd8db7a-d8ea-	We excluded most processed foods and classified foods into one of ten mutually exclus
11001	A_B_9dd8ec32-d8ea-	Based on these analyses, we collaborated with the Ghana MoFA to add nutritious food i
11002	A_B_9dde13ce-d8ea-	Additional data required for the calculation of CoNA include the nutrient composition ar

Figure 2. The information of citation sentences database

Most existing datasets contain citation categories that are too fine-grained. Actually, some categories of the citation sentence appear very infrequently or even not at all in the article. In order to focus on the research topic, we only divided the recognition of contribution into two categories, namely the contribution sentence and the non-contributory sentence. In the manual annotation process, we have summarized some signature phrases, words, and sentence patterns to assist in the research contribution annotation work. These words are also in line with the study by X. Wang et al. (2021). Some signature features are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Summary of signature features in contribution sentence

<i>Feature type</i>	<i>Example</i>
signature words	promote, landmark, important, pioneering, groundbreaking, excellent, valuable, significant, useful, elegant, fascinating, helpful, revolutionary, pathbreaking, innovative, innovatively, classic, innovation, notable, reveal, successfully,

	outstanding, promising, crucial, breakthrough, advancement.....
signature phrases	milestone report, milestone discovery, milestone study, milestone finding, important milestone, major milestone, milestone work, key milestone, milestone achievement, milestone article, milestone paper, crucial milestone, seminal study, seminal finding, seminal work, seminal paper, seminal discovery, seminal report, seminal research.....
signature sentence pattern	most frequently cited, profound effects, excellent results, provide valuable information, provide a useful, significant improvement, provided important insight, an important study by, this is the first paper.....

In this study, three people were selected to carry out the annotation work after training, and experts were requested to make decisions in case of inconsistency in annotations. Besides, the same person was asked to annotate again within a certain time interval. After continuous selection and refinement, a total of 8,800 citations have been annotated, including 2,315 positive examples. And we took out 500 negative samples and 300 positive samples at random as a test dataset.

Construction of contribution sentence identification model

For the construction of the research contribution sentence model, the BERT pre-training model (Devlin, Chang, Lee, & Toutanova, 2019), which has had good performance in various natural language processing tasks in recent years, is selected as the base model in this study. Although BERT has a nice performance of representation, it is not sufficient for BERT to learn the contributions' semantic feature because of the imbalance of positive (contribution sentences) and negative samples (non-contribution sentences). As a result, there is room for improvement in contribution sentence identification based on BERT.

Given this situation, this paper proposes a method for identifying research contribution sentences by fusing research contribution text features, we call it Feature-Spliced BERT (FS-BERT). The method draws on Target-Dependent BERT (TD-BERT) model (Gao, Feng, Song, & Wu, 2019), which takes the positioned output at the target words (refers to the signature features of Table 1 in this article) as input for classification instead of the first [CLS] tag. The main difference between our model and TD-BERT is that we splice the signature feature vector with the [CLS] vector to avoid the featureless words in some non-contributing sentences. To make it easier to see the differences, we illustrate the two structures as shown in Figure 3, TD-BERT is on the left side, and the right represents the architecture of FS-BERT. To be specific, we optimize the input layer of BERT-base model by summing the vector of signature features and then pool them on average, followed by a splicing operation with the [CLS] tag. This way could enhance the learning ability of the model for signature features, which in turn can effectively improve the performance of contribution text recognition.

Figure 3. The architecture of TD-BERT (left) and FS-BERT (right)

As a tokenizer, BERT employs WordPiece (Wu et al., 2016). The hidden state of the final layer represents the word vector matrix S_r of the sentence after the multi-layer bidirectional Transformer network.

$$S_r = [x_0, x_1, x_2, \dots, x_i, \dots, x_n, x_{n+1}] \quad (1)$$

$S_r \in R^{(n+2) \times d}$, where d is the dimension of hidden status, n is the length of the sentence. x_0 is the vector of the sentence classification tag [CLS], while x_{n+1} represents the vector of the sentence separator or end [SEP]. The signature features are represented by a sub-matrix of S_r .

$$F_r = [x_i, x_{i+1}, \dots, x_{i+m-1}] \quad (2)$$

$F_r \in R^{m \times d}$, and m represents the length of the signature feature. The mean-pooling procedure is done to the vectors of signature feature words, with the most significant features at each dimension picked.

$$V = \begin{cases} [x_0, \text{mean}\{F_r, \text{dim} = 0\}], & \text{if } F_r \in S_r \\ [x_0, x_0] & , \text{ otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$V \in R^{2 \times d}$, V is ultimately supplied to a fully-connected layer and softmax for classification.

As an illustration of the aforementioned strategy in concrete words, we use the following sentence:

s = "Indeed, a seminal contribution also made use of a similar Pd-catalysed carbonylation followed by amide formation and cyclization..."

including the signature feature "seminal contribution", so all the presentation vectors of "seminal contribution" would be taken to perform a mean pooling, then it would be spliced with [CLS] vector to be the V , V is fed into a fully-connected layer and softmax for classification at last. Moreover, if a sentence doesn't have any signature feature, then the V of the sentence is the sum of two [CLS] vectors.

All models are implemented in PyTorch, and the pretrained uncased base model of BERT is fine-tuned. We use the classification accuracy metric to measure the performance of our model and previous systems. We used the above test set to verify the identification effect between the FS-BERT and BERT-base model. As shown in Table 2 and Table 3, the macro-F1 score of the FS-BERT model exceeded that of the base model by 1.11% for the contributed sentence samples, and the overall macro-F1 score exceeded that of the base model by 0.6%. This result also highlights the superiority of the model after incorporating the feature word list. What's more, the reason why the FS-BERT model does not show a significant performance improvement over the BERT-base model is that the base model itself already performs well for

textual binary classification problems, leaving little room for improvement at a higher level. Additionally, we need to prioritize practical effects when focusing on the model.

Table 2. Contribution sentences identification results of BERT-Base model

<i>Category</i>	<i>Precision</i>	<i>Recall</i>	<i>F1-score</i>
negative	0.9160	0.9820	0.9479
positive	0.9659	0.8500	0.9043
macro avg	0.9410	0.9160	0.9261

Table 3. Contribution sentences identification results of FS-BERT model

<i>Category</i>	<i>Precision</i>	<i>Recall</i>	<i>F1-score</i>
negative	0.9517	0.9460	0.9488
positive	0.9109	0.9200	0.9154
macro avg	0.9313	0.9330	0.9321

The topic modeling technique to summarize the contribution points

With the increase in the number of publications and the ongoing expansion of citation length, there will be more contribution sentences, making it impossible to summarize contribution points manually. Therefore, it is necessary to develop a method to summarize contribution points automatically.

This study utilizes BERTopic model (Grootendorst, 2022) to summarize the contribution sentences into several aspects and extract the topics from these aspects, so as to make a comprehensive analysis of these contribution points. BERTopic is a topic model that leverages clustering techniques and a class-based variation of TF-IDF to generate coherent topic representations. To be specific, BERTopic consists of three main steps, namely document embedding, document clustering and topic representation. Following is a brief description of these three steps and the enhancements we have made to them.

BERTopic initially converts the words into vector representations using language models, which can be selected from sentence-transformers (Reimers & Gurevych, 2019). To extract the vector representation of research contribution points, we elect to use the *all-mpnet-base-v2* model, which has added a siamese network based on the *mpnet-base* (Song, Tan, Qin, Lu, & Liu, 2020) model and fine-tuned the dataset with 1 billion sentences, so that it could measure the distance between texts better.

The second stage involves the clustering of documents. Due to the fact that DBSCAN clustering method provided by the BERTopic model treats a number of samples as outliers, which may indicate that DBSCAN does not apply to our data, we attempt to cluster contribution points using Agglomerative Hierarchical clustering algorithm. This clustering approach is congruent with our notion of progressively merging comparable contribution points, hence we choose Agglomerative Hierarchical clustering algorithm as opposed to DBSCAN.

The final step is the topic representation, that is, automatically extracting labels for each cluster to grasp what a cluster is about. On the basis of BERTopic, we introduce the function of deleting stopwords to avoid stopwords such as “the” and “in” from appearing as labels. Such labels have no practical meaning and cannot represent the content of the cluster. And then we use the c-TF-IDF method proposed by BERTopic to extract the cluster labels. This strategy allows us to obtain labels that represent the cluster's content and distinguish it from other clusters.

With these procedures, we can use the topic modeling technique to separate the contribution sentences according to their semantics and summarize the topics in different clusters respectively to reveal the contribution points.

An empirical study of research contribution identification method

Based on the preceding description of the scientific contribution identification method based on semantic analysis of citation sentences, this section will use the method to empirically investigate the scientific contributions of the 2021 Physiology or Medicine Nobel Prize laureates. We take the key publications of the two laureates, David Julius (Case I) and Ardem Patapoutian (Case II), as examples to identify the research contributions from the standpoint of semantic analysis of citation sentences. Following are the specific details of the empirical study.

Data acquisition

The comprehensiveness and citation year of the citing papers have a great influence on research contribution identification for Nobel laureates. On the one hand, if we have not collected comprehensive citation data, it is of little practical significance that the identifying results are merely the subset of the real results. On the other hand, we may yield more complimentary results about their achievements if we collect too many post-award year's citing papers to analyze contributions. However, there is only one-tenth of the PubMed database in PMC, therefore, our self-built database suffers from those above limitations.

Recently, a smart citation platform called scite (Smart Citations) for discovering and evaluating scientific articles has raised attention. Smart Citations allow users to see how a publication has been cited by providing the context of the citation. In addition, the data on the platform is dedicated to full coverage in terms of discipline, including literature from various sources such as major publishers, PubMed Central, university repositories and preprint platforms, which ensures the comprehensiveness of citation data to a certain extent. Moreover, the platform can obtain not only relevant citation sentence information but also contextual information around the citation sentence, which provides a richer semantic environment for model understanding. Hence, this study uses the data from scite by setting the citation year before 2022 to do empirical research.

The first step of identifying the laureates' research contribution is to locate their representative works, then to identify the contribution from the papers that cite these works. To this end, we search for every publication's citation frequency in Web of Science core collection database according to the publication list from their research institutions or organizations and select the top 30 collections by citation frequency as the initial set. It is convenient to export citing information of every publication in the top 30 collections from scite, after that, we delete records with empty citation context. Once the relevant data has been obtained, this paper will identify the research contributions of the two laureates.

Selection of representative works based on contribution identification model

Our technique for identifying contribution sentences is applied to the collection of citations from the top 30 papers. It should be noted that the 30 articles are collected after excluding review articles published by the laureates. We then rank each paper's contribution sentences according to the number of sentences. As shown in Table 4, we list the titles of David Julius's top 10 papers based on the number of contribution sentences in each paper, as well as the frequency of citations from Web of Science as a comparison on the right. We find that there is a gap between contribution sentences ranking and citation frequency ranking. In order to determine the efficacy of the selection of representative works based on our contribution identification approach, we compared the Nobel website's key publications. Four publications

(No. 1, No. 4, No. 5, and No. 7) posted on the official website are completely covered by the ten most representative works we identified. In addition, this reflects that the contribution sentence identification model built in this paper is of some practical value.

Table 4. Contribution sentences identification results of FS-BERT model for Case I

<i>Number</i>	<i>Title</i>	<i>Contribution sen count</i>	<i>Wos rank</i>	<i>Wos frequency</i>
1	The capsaicin receptor: a heat-activated ion channel in the pain pathway	147	1	6413
2	Structure of the TRPV1 ion channel determined by electron cryo-microscopy	140	12	1095
3	TRPV1 structures in distinct conformations reveal activation mechanisms	96	21	687
4	The cloned capsaicin receptor integrates multiple pain-producing stimuli	44	3	2374
5	Identification of a cold receptor reveals a general role for TRP channels in thermosensation	38	5	1743
6	Vanilloid receptors on sensory nerves mediate the vasodilator action of anandamide	34	6	1721
7	Impaired nociception and pain sensation in mice lacking the capsaicin receptor	31	2	2629
8	New structural motif for ligand-gated ion channels defined by an ionotropic atp receptor	31	18	840
9	TRPA1 mediates the inflammatory actions of environmental irritants and proalgesic agents	25	9	1353
10	Eating disorder and epilepsy in mice lacking 5-ht2c serotonin receptors	24	13	1060

As shown in Table 5, we list the titles of Ardem Patapoutian’s top 10 papers based on the number of contribution sentences in each paper, as well as the frequency of citations from Web of Science as a comparison on the right. Also, there is a gap between contribution sentences ranking and citation frequency ranking. However, in contrast to the situation in Case I, it is only two publications (No. 1, and No. 3) on the official website that were covered by our method. In other words, the top 10 representative works we identified failed to fully cover the four papers published on the official website.

This phenomenon has some interpretability after the examination. Inevitably, however, the number of contributed sentences per article is also related to its publication duration. Ardem Patapoutian used the chemical substance menthol to identify TRPM8, a receptor that was shown to be activated by cold in 2002. His group continued this research over the next few years until, in 2010, he made the groundbreaking discovery of a new and entirely unknown mechanosensitive ion channel, named Piezo1. This was followed by the discovery of pizeo2, which was found to express high levels in sensory neurons. The breakthrough by Patapoutian led to a series of papers from his and other groups, demonstrating that the Piezo2 ion channel is essential for the sense of touch. As a result, the two uncovered publications lack an edge in terms of citation time, preventing them from being ranked among the 10 most representative

works. On the other side, it is also due to the fact that we only chose citations for each publication for analysis up to 2021, which might potentially influence the identification findings.

Table 5. Contribution sentences identification results of FS-BERT model for Case II

<i>Number</i>	<i>Title</i>	<i>Contribution sen count</i>	<i>Wos rank</i>	<i>Wos frequency</i>
1	Piezo1 and Piezo2 are essential components of distinct mechanically activated cation channels	63	4	1373
2	SWELL1, a plasma membrane protein, is an essential component of volume-regulated anion channel	35	20	360
3	A TRP channel that senses cold stimuli and menthol	34	2	1623
4	ANKTM1, a TRP-like channel expressed in nociceptive neurons, is activated by cold temperatures	26	1	1901
5	Noxious compounds activate TRPA1 ion channels through covalent modification of cysteines	19	7	900
6	Piezo proteins are pore-forming subunits of mechanically activated channels	18	10	601
7	Piezo2 is required for merkel-cell mechanotransduction	16	19	420
8	TRPM8 is required for cold sensation in mice	13	9	614
9	Impaired thermosensation in mice lacking TRPV3, a heat and camphor sensor in the skin	12	13	546
10	Noxious cold ion channel TRPA1 is activated by pungent compounds and bradykinin	11	3	1407

In addition to the selection of representative works, this paper also provides an in-depth analysis of the identified contribution sentences. There are many specific descriptions of contribution sentences that have significant and far-reaching impacts on the whole field of research. But due to the limitation of space, we can only select several representative sentences to analyze two laureates' research contributions, which are sorted by timeline. Figure 4 lists the analysis result of Case I based on its contribution sentences; Figure 5 lists the analysis result of Case II based on its contribution sentences. There is a lot of valuable information contained in contribution sentences, which provide solid evidence to support a more comprehensive and in-depth understanding of the research contribution of the article and its long-term impact on subsequent research. Overall, there is a progressive change over time from micro to macro effect in the scope of the contributions' influence in both cases.

Figure 4. The contribution analysis for Case I

Figure 5. The contribution analysis for Case II

Summary of research contribution points

In order to facilitate the verification against the press release, we only choose the eight key publications in the Nobel press release as experimental subjects to identify two laureates' research contributions. After identifying the contribution sentences of each of the four main publications for each laureate, we get 260 contribution sentences from Case I, and 130 contribution sentences from Case II. And then, we preprocess these sentences, including removing some reference marks such as “[18]”, “*et al.*” and “*person + year*”, to further purify the semantic environment.

By clustering and topic modeling, we can get labels that reflect the content of a cluster and distinguish it from other clusters. When it comes to the number of clusters, we determine the most suitable number for each case through experiments. And we got better results when we set 2 classes in Case I and 3 classes in Case II. The summary of the research contribution point is shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Summary of the research contribution points for the two laureates

<i>Case</i>	<i>Research contribution points</i>
Case I	① trpv1_capsaicin_receptor_channel ② trpv1_trpm8_neurons_channel
Case II	① piezo1_piezo_channels_piezo2 ② neurons_piezo2_drg_channels ③ trpm8_cold_menthol_channel

We backtrack the original contribution sentences for each class cluster topic, it can be seen that these clustering topics are basically able to reflect two laureates' research contributions. Case I focuses primarily on two aspects of Julius's research contribution, one of which is the discovery of the capsaicin receptor (TRPV1), a heat and nociceptive channel. His second contribution to science is the identification of some ion channels associated with TRPV1 and TRPM8. Case II mainly focuses on three aspects of Patapoutian's research contribution. One of which is the discovery of Piezo1 and Piezo2 for mechanosensitive ion channels; The second is that he found the Piezo2 ion channel is essential for the sense of touch; And the last is the identification of other ion channels associated with cold sensing such as TRPM8 (the two laureates independently identified TRPM8 respectively).

Discussion and conclusion

This paper proposes a method to identify research contributions based on semantic analysis of citation sentences, which makes up for the subjectivity and limitation of identifying scientific research contributions solely from the content of papers. Furthermore, the method offers readers a novel perspective on mining a paper's contribution from the external citation environment. It provides a fine-grained evidence-based basis for the reform of the evaluation system. Beyond that, it can also give an appropriate framework for the selection of representative works.

Our research contribution identification model contains two parts. One part is to construct a contribution sentence identification model based on FS-BERT to analyze research contribution from the perspective of sentence level, this is backed up by high-quality annotation data; the other part is the summarization of contribution points based on contribution sentences. In the end, we conduct empirical research using the key publications from the 2021 Physiology or Medicine Nobel Prize laureates. After the comparison with the award speech, we preliminarily realize the identification of research contributions for the 2021 Physiology or Medicine Nobel Prize laureates. It is our interest to include other domains of Nobel Prizes when we have access

to a more comprehensive full-text source. We also plan to further analyze the composition mode of research contribution in citation sentences at the phrase level and divide the contribution into the more fine-grained aspect at the sentence level, such as micro and macro contributions. Aside from this, the method of selecting representative works requires additional investigation, for instance, we need to consider how to add the dimension of citation time.

There are, of course, some limitations to this approach. In theory, the method applies to all disciplines, but it has only been empirically demonstrated in the biomedical field, so we need to use more domain data to verify the robustness and generalization ability of the method. On the other hand, the problems of clustering label generation and the reference resolution in sentences are also worth further exploration.

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